

A Montecarlo Reactive Navigation Algorithm for a Dual Arm Aerial Robot

Fran Real¹, Ángel R. Castaño¹, Jesús Capitán¹

Robotics, Vision and Control Group
University of Seville
Seville, Spain
[freal,castano,jcapitan]@us.es

Abstract. In this paper, we propose a reactive algorithm for a dual arm aerial robot during its navigation phase. This algorithm takes into account not only the aerial platform dynamics but also the constraints imposed by the dual-arm manipulator. The UAV is fully and continuously controlled using velocity commands but the arms are only allowed to move between a set of predefined configurations. The arms configurations are bounded in order to achieve a reduced solution space for collision checking. The reactive navigation algorithm is based on commands from a higher-level path planner and receives as input point-cloud sensor readings. This work is within the framework of the AEROARMS project, so we consider the dual-arm aerial platform developed in the project. Thus, a simple but realistic model for velocity dynamics of the mentioned UAV has been obtained by means of real data, and the proposed method has been tested in a SITL simulation framework.

Keywords: Reactive navigation; aerial robotics; dual arm manipulator

1 Introduction

In order to navigate with an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) in complex environments like the industrial inspection and maintenance scenarios addressed in the AEROARMS¹ project, an autonomous mobile robot needs to reach a compromise between the need for reacting to unexpected events and the need for having efficient and optimized trajectories. Usually, path-planning methods work in two steps: in the first one, a global path in a previous map is calculated, and in the second step, the robot reads the sensor data and the local trajectory is modified in a reactive way (a planner is called reactive if it considers only the currently visible obstacles for planning the next step). That allows the path-adaptation mechanism to cope with unexpected obstacles or dynamic environments. These methods calculate the global trajectory off-line in an *a priori* known map and the local modifications are made continuously based on the sensor data while the robot is moving.

¹ <https://aeroarms-project.eu/>

The reason for using a two-level planning approach is due to the high computational cost required in most motion-planning techniques to achieve an updated environment model and to plan a smooth and dynamically adapted trajectory. Moreover, the use of a two-level planner strategy decreases the computational cost due to the fact that the global planner is activated occasionally (it can be done off-line) and the local planner, which is much faster, runs on-line.

In local path planning, which is the main focus of this paper, we can mention reactive collision avoidance methods such as (see [3]): potential fields, VFH, ND, DWA, velocity obstacles (ORCA). Also [4] provides a good introduction to terminology in UAV path planning and classification of methods.

However, many traditional methods for global path planning are being enhanced lately in order to be able to cope with dynamic environments in a reactive manner. In this sense, probabilistic sample-based planners are commonplace. There is an interesting review in [2], where they explain the basics for RRT and PRM, and give an overview of how to select different parameters. They have also specific sections for optimal sampled-based planners (e.g., RRT*, PRM*), kinodynamic planning and planners for dynamic and uncertain environments. RRTX [8] is a really recent novel algorithm. It is an asymptotically optimal sampling-based motion planning algorithm for real-time navigation in dynamic environments (containing obstacles that unpredictably appear, disappear, and move).

Collision checking is considered to be the most expensive computational bottleneck in sampling-based motion planning algorithms, and a problem suitable for parallelization. [1] propose a new collision-checking technique in order to save time by avoiding checking all points. The method could be applied to different planners and may be of interest in problems with complex collision-checking such as AEROARMS. Moreover, [9] present a novel approach to perform fast probabilistic collision checking in high-dimensional configuration spaces to accelerate the performance of sampling-based motion planning. The idea is to maintain a database with prior collision-checking queries and estimate the collision probability for new queries, avoiding additional actual collision checks for unnecessary cases.

Some works also apply parallelization techniques to speed up the planning process. For instance, [5] is a paper of interest for using GPUs to solve planning problems. In that case, they use CUDA to parallelize the MCVI solver for POMP problems. In [10], a parallel implementation for RRT is proposed using GPU. They use some benchmark scenarios and algorithm implementations from the library OMPL for comparison.

The main contribution of this paper is to present a reactive algorithm for local navigation, which takes into account not only the UAV itself but also the constraints imposed by the onboard manipulator. Our approach is sampling-based and considers models for the whole platform (UAV plus manipulator) to predict trajectories ahead and check collisions. In order to simplify the joint solution space, the configuration space for the arms is discretized, i.e., only a small set of typical configurations are allowed. A key point of our algorithm is

that it is well suited for parallelization, which is our final goal. The idea is to implement later the reactive navigation using CUDA and an NVIDIA Jetson TX1 GPU in order to make the real-time response faster, which is needed for navigation in complex and dynamic scenarios.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the dual arm aerial robot developed in the AEROARMS project; Section 3 is devoted to the overall architecture of the navigation system; Section 4 describes our Montecarlo reactive algorithm proposed; and Section 5 and Section 6 are dedicated to the simulation results and conclusions obtained, respectively.

2 Dual-arm Aerial Robot

In this section, we present briefly the dual-arm aerial platform that we have developed for the AEROARMS project. Our reactive algorithm will be used to navigate this platform around a complex scenario, placing the arms in different configurations.

The UAV is an hexarotor with two human-size arms attached to the chassis, as shown in Figure 1. A more detailed description of the arms mounted on board can be found in [11].

Fig. 1. Different views of the dual-arm aerial platform.

The size of the hexarotor is $1.18 \times 1.18 \times 0.5m$ (including rotor blades), it weighs $6.5kg$ (including batteries, arms, sensors and electronics), its MTOW is $10kg$ and its flight time is 20 minutes. The structure is made of carbon fiber, it is equipped with brushless engines T-Motor MN4006 380KV and 15×5 carbon fiber propellers. There are three onboard processors: a Pixhawk PX4 for UAV control and state estimation, an Odroid board to interface the arms and a general purpose Intel NUC i7 processor. The robot primary sensors are a GPS and a ZED stereo camera, which provides a 3D point cloud for navigation.

The aerial robot can be commanded in velocity through the Pixhawk board and each joint of the dual arms can be commanded in position through the Odroid board. The velocity dynamics model of the aerial robot has been ex-

perimentally obtained from real data. Figure 2 shows that the forward velocity dynamics (v_x) and position (x) estimations match quite well with real data.

Fig. 2. Real and modelled longitudinal speed (v_x) and position (x) of our dual-arm aerial robot.

3 Navigation Architecture

As many other works from the state of art [1, 7, 6], a navigation framework with several layers have been designed (see Figure 3) for our platform. The idea is to have global and/or local planners providing plans over a precomputed map, and then performing obstacle avoidance while trying to follow the plan using sensor inputs. The outputs of the planner modules are the position/velocity of the UAV and the joints angles of the dual manipulator. These values are the inputs for the *Local Navigation and Operation* module, which modifies these setpoints taking into account point-cloud sensor readings.

In order to perform a mission with the UAV, two different modes of operation are considered: the *Navigation* mode and the *Manipulation* mode. In the *Navigation* mode, the UAV travels to the operation point (the UAV is aimed for inspection) using continuous velocity commands, but only a set of discrete configurations for the dual arm (see Figure 4) are allowed. Thus, in this mode the arms move slowly, just to change their configuration, while the UAV is allowed to move freely. Therefore, the solution space is reduced and can be explored more easily for collision checking.

Fig. 3. Overall navigation architecture for the UAV.

Fig. 4. Set of configurations considered for the arms.

In the *Manipulation* mode the UAV moves slowly, near the operation point, but the arms are fully and continuously controlled.

In this paper a Montecarlo reactive algorithm is proposed for the *Navigation* mode. It is based on trajectory rollouts where the model of the UAV together with the arms configuration are taken into account to check for collisions efficiently, which is one of the bottlenecks in terms of computational load for obstacle avoidance in 3D environments [1, 9].

4 Montecarlo Reactive Navigation Algorithm

Given the next waypoint provided by the global planner, a desired velocity vector v_p can be computed for the reactive navigation module. Then, a Montecarlo approach is followed to sample multiple times the solution space (i.e., continuous 3D velocity vectors and discrete arms configurations) and simulate the trajectories ahead, checking for collisions. Thus, several simulations are performed, using different input values u_i (velocity vector) and k (arms configuration) and taking into account the point-cloud obtained from the ZED stereo camera.

The algorithm executes the following steps for each simulation:

1. Select control input u_i , sampled with a bias around v_p .
2. Sample configuration for the arms k .
3. Predict robot trajectory within time T , given u_i (using the model presented in Section 2).
4. Check collisions:
 - A simple spherical representation of the robot volume is placed around each position.
 - Different volume radii can be used depending on the arm configuration k .
 - Trajectories where point-cloud particles lie within the object volume are discarded and trajectories without collisions are evaluated.
5. Evaluate path for u_i and k using a cost index J_{ik} that takes into account the distance from the path endpoint to the goal and the minimum distance from the point-cloud to the path.

After N random simulations, the algorithm selects the pair (u_i, k) with the lowest J_{ik} , which is defined in the following equation:

$$J_{ik} = \frac{\text{dist}(\text{goal}, \text{pos}_i(t = T))}{\text{dist}(\text{goal}, \text{pos}_i(t = 0))} + \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{r_k}{\min[\text{dist}(p_j, \text{pos}_{ik}(t = 0, t = T))]} \quad (1)$$

where

r_k : radius for configuration k

p_j : point from a point-cloud with M points

$\text{pos}_i(t)$: position at time t of simulation with u_i

$\text{pos}_{ik}(t = t_1, t = t_2)$: trajectory $t_1 \rightarrow t_2$ with u_i and configuration k

In order not to sample the whole 3D space looking for velocity vectors, the vector u_i is sampled with a bias around the velocity v_p . This one is computed taken into account the direction of the next waypoint (goal) provided by the global planner (see Figure 5). The azimuth and polar components of the vector are sampled using gaussian distributions with standard deviations σ_θ and σ_φ but the module is sampled using a triangular distribution with lower limit 0, upper limit $\|v_p\|$ and mode $K_v \cdot \|v_p\|$ (where $K_v \in [0, 1]$) as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Left, velocity vector computed taken into account the next goal from the global planner. Right, triangular probability distribution used to sample velocity module with $K_v = 0.8$.

5 Experimental Results

In this section, we present some preliminary results of the navigation algorithm with a simulated environment. We first explain the simulation framework, and later the adjustment of parameters and results.

5.1 Simulation Framework

A simulation framework have been developed to validate and test the reactive navigation algorithm. A precise 3D model of the dual-arm aerial robot was developed in Gazebo, including point-cloud sensors. Also, different test scenarios, such as an industrial plant (see Figure 6), were created. In order to make the simulations as close as possible to the real robot, a Software-In-The-Loop (SITL) framework was developed, which is able to emulate the interfaces of the actual aerial platform, both in terms of vehicle controller and point-cloud sensors. For that, the same Pixhawk software stack that runs in the onboard Pixhawk PX4 was compiled and run in the simulator.

The complete framework includes a laptop running a server with the scenario, the SITL and the robot model in Gazebo. This laptop is connected through

TCP/IP to a Jetson TX1 GPU (see Figure 6) that executes the reactive algorithm using a preloaded point-cloud, i.e., the camera is not read in real time.

Fig. 6. Simulation framework. Left, industrial plant scenario in Gazebo. Right, simulation setup with server laptop and GPU.

5.2 Parameter Tuning and Simulation Results

Several simulations were performed to validate the reactive navigation algorithm proposed and to tune the parameters. We noticed empirically that the following values were adequate for our scenario:

- Time horizon: $T = 3s$
- Number of samples: $N = 25$
- Probability distribution parameters: $\sigma_\theta = \frac{\pi}{4}, \sigma_\varphi = \frac{\pi}{8}$

Although the reactive algorithm was run with a GPU fully integrated, the simulation results shown in this paper were obtained with a non-parallel implementation. The parallelized version of the reactive algorithm is still an ongoing work. Note also that the configuration of the arms was not very relevant for the experiments shown. We are planning to navigate with more complex scenarios where the arms will need to be expanded or contracted so that the UAV passes through.

An illustrative simulated scenario is shown in Figure 7. There are two walls that obstruct the path provided by the global plan. These obstacles were not considered in the original map but they were detected by the onboard point-cloud sensors.

As shown in Figures 8 and 9 the trajectory planned originally (blue line) takes the robot through the two walls because these obstacles were not considered in the map. However, our reactive algorithm, based on the input from the point-cloud sensor, keeps the first wall on the left while moving forward and then goes up and down to avoid the front wall. The actual trajectory followed by the UAV is depicted in purple and the arrows show some of the sampled velocity vectors considered in each iteration.

Fig. 7. Simulated scenario in Gazebo with two obstacles that obstruct the original path planned for the UAV.

Fig. 8. Simulated navigation in scenario with two walls: side view.

Fig. 9. Simulated navigation in scenario with two walls: top view.

In Figure 10 the robot must avoid a "U" shape obstacle that was not considered in the plan originally. The desired velocity vector v_p (bold blue arrow) is always pointing to the goal position (blue sphere). When the onboard sensors detect the obstacle (red), the reactive algorithm evaluates different trajectories to avoid it. Evaluated trajectories that cause a collision are depicted in red and trajectories considered in the cost function J_{ik} are depicted in green. Then, u_i with the lowest cost function is selected (bold green arrow). The reactive algorithm manages to take the robot to the target position without re-planning and computing new intermediate goals.

Fig. 10. Simulated scenario with a "U" shape obstacle.

6 Conclusions

The reactive algorithm proposed has shown a good performance when dealing with unplanned obstacles in real 3D scenarios without the need to replan or update a local map. Thanks to the SITL simulation framework a good correlation between simulation and experimental results with the real platform is expected. The implementation in the actual dual-arm aerial robot is currently an ongoing work that will allow us to validate the whole system in field tests. Moreover, extensive validation in more complex scenarios where arms configurations are critical, and a parallel implementation of the reactive algorithm using a Jetson TX1 GPU, are also ongoing work.

Acknowledgements. This work has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644271 (AEROARMS).

References

1. Bialkowski, J., Otte, M., Karaman, S., Frazzoli, E.: Efficient collision checking in sampling-based motion planning via safety certificates. *The International Journal of Robotics Research* 35(7), 767–796 (jun 2016), <http://ijr.sagepub.com/content/35/7/767.abstract> <http://ijr.sagepub.com/cgi/doi/10.1177/0278364915625345>
2. Elbanhawi, M., Simic, M.: Sampling-Based Robot Motion Planning: A Review. *IEEE Access* 2, 56–77 (2014), <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/lpdocs/epic03/wrapper.htm?arnumber=6722915>
3. Garrido, S., Moreno, L., Blanco, D., Munoz, M.L.: Sensor-based global planning for mobile robot navigation. *Robotica* 25(2), 189–199 (2007)
4. Goerzen, C., Kong, Z., Mettler, B.: A Survey of Motion Planning Algorithms from the Perspective of Autonomous UAV Guidance. *Journal of Intelligent and Robotic Systems* 57(1-4), 65–100 (jan 2010), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10846-009-9383-1> <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10846-009-9383-1>
5. Lee, T., Kim, Y.J.: Massively parallel motion planning algorithms under uncertainty using POMDP. *The International Journal of Robotics Research* 35(8), 928–942 (jul 2016), <http://ijr.sagepub.com/content/35/8/928.abstract> <http://ijr.sagepub.com/cgi/doi/10.1177/0278364915594856>
6. Nieuwenhuisen, M., Droschel, D., Beul, M., Behnke, S.: Autonomous navigation for micro aerial vehicles in complex gnss-denied environments. *Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems* 84(1), 199–216 (Dec 2016), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10846-015-0274-3>
7. Nuske, S., Choudhury, S., Jain, S., Chambers, A., Yoder, L., Scherer, S., Chamberlain, L., Cover, H., Singh, S.: Autonomous Exploration and Motion Planning for an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Navigating Rivers. *Journal of Field Robotics* 32(8), 1141–1162 (dec 2015), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/rob.21596> <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1002/rob.21596>
8. Otte, M., Frazzoli, E.: RRTX: Asymptotically optimal single-query sampling-based motion planning with quick replanning. *The International Journal of Robotics Research* 35(7), 797–822 (jun 2016), <http://ijr.sagepub.com/content/35/7/797.abstract> <http://ijr.sagepub.com/cgi/doi/10.1177/0278364915594679>
9. Pan, J., Manocha, D.: Fast probabilistic collision checking for sampling-based motion planning using locality-sensitive hashing. *The International Journal of Robotics Research* 35(12), 1477–1496 (oct 2016), <http://ijr.sagepub.com/content/35/12/1477.abstract> <http://ijr.sagepub.com/cgi/doi/10.1177/0278364916640908>
10. Park, C., Pan, J., Manocha, D.: Parallel Motion Planning Using Poisson-Disk Sampling. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics* 33(2), 359–371 (2017)
11. Suarez, A., Jimenez-Cano, A.E., Vega, V.M., Heredia, G., Rodriguez-Castaño, A., Ollero, A.: Lightweight and human-size dual arm aerial manipulator. 2017 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS) (2017)